

Myiasis and its management

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Introduction

Myiasis is a Greek work derived from “Myia” – refers to animal disease due to fly larva. Zumpt defined myiasis as Infestation of live human and vertebrate animals with larvae of dipteran fly which atleast for certain period feed on host’s dead or living tissues, liquid body substances or ingested food. In sheep it is referred to as “strike” or blow fly myiasis. Generally caused by larvae of *Chrysomia*, *Lucilia*, *Phormia* and *Calliphora*.

Classification of myiasis

Anatomical

- Cutaneous myiasis – Eg: *Lucilia*, *Chrysomia*
- Nasal myiasis – Eg: *Oestrus ovis*
- Gastric/intestinal myiasis Eg: *Gasterophilus*

Cutaneous myiasis

- Mainly caused by larva of blow flies, Abundant in late spring and early summer.
- Flies feed on liquefied protein.
- Larva growth depends on food obtained from either living or dead carcasses of various animals on which adult lay eggs.

Parasitological

Obligatory myiasis: Requires live host to develop and cause myiasis Eg: *Oestrus ovis*

Facultative myiasis: Develops both on live animals or dead organic matter

Eg: *Lucilia* sp./*Chrysomia* sp.

Accidental myiasis: When egg or larva of fly is accidentally swallowed Eg: *Musca* sp.

Miscellaneous Myiasis

- Accidental but not involving GI tract when wrong host involved.
- Eggs laid in atypical sites.
- Eg: *Musca* in urethra, bladder in human.

Classification of myiasis causing flies

Primary flies	Secondary flies	Tertiary flies
Initiates strike by laying eggs living sheep	Lays eggs on sheep already struck-larva extends injury done by primary flies	Comes last and larva causes further damage
Eg: <i>Lucilia cuprina</i> <i>Lucilia sericata</i>	Eg: <i>Chrysomya</i> sp.	Eg: <i>Musca domestica</i>

Epizootiology

Depends on prevalence of flies and susceptibility of sheep.

Prevalence of flies depends on:

- Season- temperature, humidity, Abundance of food
- Larvae obtains food from either living sheep or carrion on which adult lay eggs.

Susceptibility of sheep - myiasis (depends on inherent and temporary factors):

Area	Name
Breech	Breech strike, crutch strike
Tail	Tail strike
In Rams, penile sheath has narrow opening and soiled by urine	Pizzle strike
Rams with deep head folds or with horns lying close to head – sweaty condition of head	Poll strike

Pathogenesis

- Presence of wound and bacterial decomposition lead to odour that attracts flies.
- Larva of primary flies initiate attack and create favourable conditions for secondary flies.
- They secrete proteolytic enzymes, digest and liquefy tissues and feed on predigested materials.
- Secondary flies form tunnels in tissues and underneath skin.
- Central portion of lesion may heal with formation of thick scab.
- Smell emanating from lesion attracts other flies to deposit eggs in it.
- Irritation, lack of proper feed intake occurs.
- Immediate cause of death in severely affected animals - toxemia
- Toxemia due to absorption of substances from lesions or even septicemia

Clinical signs

- Irritation, animal stands with its head down

- Attempts to bite affected area
- If lesion in tail region, animal stamps or jerks its hind legs, wags its tail
- Examination reveals discolored moist wool with bad odor and presence of foul-smelling liquid
- Trimming wool reveals presence of maggots
- Progression of disease lead to malnutrition, Loss of production, Death
- Condition called lightning strike occurs when toxemia / septicemia occurs wherein animals dies within few days of strike
- **Financial loss:**
 - Decrease in value of fleece
 - Reduction in meat and milk production

Diagnosis

- Clinical signs, trimming wool helps to reveal presence of larvae

Treatment

- Clip wool around area
 - Removal of maggots (repellents like turpentine)
 - Clean with antiseptics (Potassium permanganate)
 - Hydrogen peroxide – removing scab and dead tissue
 - Dress with insecticide and antiseptics
 - Injection or pour on – Ivermectin @ 200µg/Kg BW
 - Render sheep less attractive to flies by
- a) Selective breeding to eliminate folds in poll region / narrow breech
 - b) Surgical removal of breech folds - **Mule's operation**
 - Crescentic area on either side of urinogenital area is removed, resultant scarring flattens skin – effective for breech strike
 - ‘**Chemical mule sing**’ - 40% phenol when applied along prepuce of young withers or even in breech region
 - c) Docking at 4th instead of 2nd coccygeal vertebrae reduces strike. (2nd coccygeal region result in stump surrounded by folds – “rose tail” appearance)
 - d) Crutching - Regular clipping of wool around tail, breech to prevent soiling of wool
 - e) Dagging - Removal of fecal soiled wool
 - Burial or burning of carcasses
 - Use of chemicals – Insecticides in wounds infested with larvae

References

Soulsby, E.J.L., 1982. (7th Ed.). Helminths, Arthropods and Protozoa of domesticated animals, 291.